

Making Visible the Invisible: Unveiling Global Shifts, Key Research Fronts and Emerging Trends in Renewable Energy Research

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Abstract

This article presents a global map of the scientific landscape in renewable energy, highlighting key research fronts and their evolution over time. Drawing from 779,434 publications in the Scopus database (2000–2022), we used the second derivative analysis of publication trends to identify three distinct periods: 2000–2012, 2013–2019, and 2020–2022. Their development is illustrated through the use of overlay mapping techniques. The study identifies three principal research fronts: the technological structure of renewable energies (wind and photovoltaic), biofuel generation from biomass, and sustainability-focused policy research. Emerging fronts include energy storage technologies, solar and geothermal energy generation, and applications of artificial intelligence in renewable energy systems. These findings provide insight into major transitions in the global energy research ecosystem and offer a valuable framework for assessing national scientific and technological capacities. They also support strategic planning in research and development, as well as science and technology policymaking.

Keywords: Renewable Energy; Sustainability and Environment; Scientific Output; Research Fronts; Emerging Technologies; Longitudinal Scientometric Analysis.

Highlights

- Overlay mapping reveals the scientific structure and research fronts in Renewable Energies.
- Three key fronts: wind-photovoltaic, biomass biofuels, and SDG policies in RE.
- Emerging trends: AI, energy storage (batteries), and solar-geothermal generation.
- Second derivative analysis identifies three major RE research periods (2000–2022).
- Methodology applicable to any field, revealing structure and key research fronts.

Word Count: 5687 words excluding title, author names and affiliations, keywords, abbreviations list, table/figures captions, acknowledgements, supplementary information, data availability and references

List of abbreviations

GHG: Greenhouse Gases

PV: Photovoltaic

RE: Renewable Energy

SDG: Sustainable Development Goals

SS: Scientific Systems

USA: United States of America

WoS: Web of Science

1. Introduction

Fossil fuels account for 80% of the global energy consumption and, according to the International Energy Agency (IEA), remain the primary source of energy generation [1]. However, their widespread use significantly contributes to increased greenhouse gas emissions (GHG), responsible for global warming and climate change deterioration. In response, renewable energies (RE) have emerged as a strategic alternative, distinguished by their ability to decarbonize energy systems and mitigate environmental damage [2]. According to the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), in 2022, RE accounted for 29% of the world's electricity generation capacity, reflecting significant progress towards a more sustainable energy future [3].

The increasing adoption of clean and sustainable energy sources by various countries and international organizations reflects a global commitment to a more environmentally responsible future [4]. In this context, research is crucial, fostering the development and implementation of renewable technologies that facilitate the transition to more sustainable energy systems [5]. This trend has led to a notable increase in scientific production related to RE, consolidating a dynamic and expanding field within global scientific literature.

According to Elsevier's Scopus database, scientific literature on sustainability, environment, and RE has experienced steady growth, with an average annual rate of 0.15% over the past 23 years. This increase represents a cumulative output of 779,434 documents published between 2000 and 2022 (Fig. 1-left). Globally, China leads scientific production in RE, with 20.9% of the total, followed by the United States (11.1%) and India (6.5%). Other prominent countries include the United Kingdom, Germany, South Korea, Italy, Spain, Japan, and Canada, with contributions ranging between 2.3% and 3.7% (Fig. 1-right). These countries play a predominant role in the knowledge generation of RE, despite global disparities in RE investment and development.

Fig. 1. Growth of publications in Renewable Energy (left). Countries with the highest production of scientific documents on Renewable Energy in the world (right).

Bibliometric techniques are a key tool for analyzing the growth and dynamics of scientific production in the RE field. These techniques enable the identification of patterns, trends, and underlying factors that foster knowledge development at a global, regional, country, institutional, and researcher level, over time. Additionally, they provide valuable insights into the interactions among research works, technological innovation, and the adoption of sustainable energy policies, solidifying their utility in studying the global progress of RE [6].

Bibliometric techniques have been used in different studies. For example, Romo-Fernández et al. [7] analyzed publications regarding "Renewable Energies, Sustainability, and Environment" using Scopus data between 2003 and 2008. They identified a global increase in scientific production, highlighting the United States, China, the United Kingdom, India, Turkey, and Japan as the main contributors. These authors classified countries into five groups based on their specialization and production, revealing remarkable differences in terms of impact and international recognition. However, this study only focused on the quantity and quality of publications, without analyzing the relevant topics within RE during that period.

Manzano-Agugliaro et al. [5] reviewed scientific production regarding RE (solar, wind, biomass, hydroelectric, and geothermal), between 1979 and 2009, using Web of Science (WoS) data. They found that biomass was the most studied RE (70-80% of the total production), mainly by a few countries. The United States led research in solar, wind, and geothermal energies, while China stood out in hydroelectric and biomass energies. Their findings show trends and the geographic disparity in technology development.

Rizzi et al. [8] analyzed global scientific production regarding five RE areas: biomass, geothermal, hydroelectric, solar, and wind. They used WoS data from 1992 to 2011 and combined bibliometrics with expert debates analysis. They identified that solar energy, biomass, and wind attracted the most interest, correlating this with resource availability and technology flexibility, and growth scale.

Aleixandre-Tudo et al. [9] analyzed scientific production, financing, international collaboration, and the most cited articles in the RE field, using data from WoS from 2007 to 2016. Publications mainly focused on wind, solar, and biomass energies. The United States, China, the United Kingdom, Germany, and Spain were the main producers. Strong international collaboration was found particularly between the

US, China, and the European Union. The most cited articles addressed topics like nanostructures, semiconductors, storage, sustainability, and energy efficiency.

Additionally, there have been regional and national studies regarding RE [10]. These include research on the main countries of the European Union [11], as well as individual studies on Turkey [12], Mexico [13], Russia [14], Nigeria [15], Poland [16], and comparative studies between Spain and Germany on solar energy [17, 18]. Emerging technologies in solar and photovoltaic (PV) energy [19, 20, 21, 22, 23], hydroelectric [24], biomass [25], biodiesel [26], and specialized studies on topics such as energy systems [27], hydrogen storage and production [28, 29, 30, 31], RE grid integration [32, 33, 34], thermal energy storage [35, 36, 37, 38, 39], applications in advanced materials like graphene [4], and optimization through artificial intelligence (AI) applied to various RE [40] have also been explored. This diversity of studies emphasizes the importance of identifying thematic trends in RE and their evolution to guide the design and analysis of scientific policies.

In this context, this study has three main objectives: (1) to visualize and identify the main research fronts in RE worldwide; (2) to present, through a longitudinal study and temporal periods, the evolution of these fronts; and (3) to provide a comprehensive vision of RE development, identifying the most relevant current scientific topics.

2. Materials and Methods

The methodology involved several techniques to process and analyze the information. Figure 2 illustrates a diagram with eight consecutive steps detailing the methodological process, adapted from Muñoz-Ecija et al. [41] and Cobo et al. [42]. This approach reveals the complexity and evolution of RE research lines worldwide over a 23-year period (2000-2022).

Fig. 2. Methodological steps for delimiting the descriptors in renewable energy.

Our primary information source was the Scopus database, chosen for its broader coverage and larger volume of indexed publications compared to WoS [43, 44, 45]. Scopus classifies its journals and papers using the All Science Journal Classification Codes (ASJC), with code 2105 corresponding to "Renewable Energies, Sustainability, and Environment." On April 15, 2024, we searched for: SUBJTERMS (2105) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND PUBYEAR < 2023, retrieving 779,434 indexed documents for the period 2000-2022.

To identify temporal periods for the longitudinal study, we linked RE document growth with a second derivative criterion analysis (Fig. 3). This technique identifies growth rate inflection points where

significant changes occurred [46], enabling study period segmentation into three temporal periods: 2000-2012, 2013-2019, and 2020-2022, while helping detect key patterns and trends in scientific production [47].

Fig. 3. Temporal Periods of Publications about Renewable Energy 2000-2022.

Co-word analysis [48] is a highly effective method for identifying the cognitive structure of a research area and its evolution [49]. To display this structure, we used Author Keywords (authors' descriptive terms) as the unit of analysis, and their co-occurrence in documents as the unit of measurement. For normalization, we created a specific thesaurus with 25,728 descriptors, standardizing plural and singular forms, abbreviations, acronyms, and terms [50].

We used VOSviewer software to generate a cognitive structure and identify main research fronts. This free software displays terms as nodes, sized proportionally to their frequency, while co-occurrence indicates term distance and relationship strength. Thematic clusters or research fronts are color-coded [51]. High-frequency terms initially indicate research hotspots [46]. For computational efficiency, we set a co-occurrence threshold of ≥ 10 , generating a cognitive structure of 32,935 terms within five research fronts.

Influence indicators are crucial for understanding cognitive and research network structure and impact. We used the Weight Total Link Strength (Score) to measure the total link strength between a term and its connected terms [49, 51, 52]. VOSviewer also allowed assigning attributes to visualization elements, highlighting their importance and other properties in shaping the thematic structure.

Finally, we employed overlay maps to explore RE's cognitive structure, providing a comprehensive view of research area changes over time [53]. This enabled visualization of term emergence, consolidation, or disappearance, detection of connection patterns, network structural changes, and other key factors in global scientific production dynamics [54, 55].

Results and Discussion

This section presents the five main RE research fronts crucial for understanding global research priorities and trends. Figure 4 displays a cognitive map highlighting these fronts using "Score" and frequency indicators. The results are ordered descendingly, emphasizing the most relevant fronts and terms.

Worldwide, we identified five major research fronts: three consolidated – Sustainability Policy (red), Structure in Renewable Energies (green), and Biofuel Generation (blue); and two emerging – RE Storage (yellow) and Solar Energy Generation (purple)

Fig. 4. Cognitive map of scientific production in Renewable Energy in the world.

Note: The following link allows the reader to view the maps and networks in VOSviewer:

<https://tinyurl.com/2bxszg4v>. Please note that for very large domains, for example, the world map, a computer with more than 16 GB of RAM is required.

3.1. Research Fronts in Renewable Energies Worldwide

The research front *Structure in Renewable Energies* (green) ranks first, representing 28% of the production, including 5,746 terms (23% of the total network), with *renewable energy* being the most relevant descriptor (Score: 10,911). This descriptor emphasizes the natural regeneration of RE sources like solar-photovoltaic, wind, hydroelectric, geothermal, biomass, and tidal energy. Additionally, this front highlights research on emerging technologies to improve the efficiency of prediction, production,

optimization of energy storage, and energy demand in RE systems. This front also extends to technological products related to electric vehicles.

The second most influential research front is *Biofuel Generation* (blue), which accounts for 23% of the top-ranked descriptors, and 21% of the total terms (5,380). The main term is *biomass* with a score of 7,560. *Biomass* stands out as a key source for mitigating climate change with bioproducts such as *biodiesel*, *biogas*, and *hydrogen*. These *biofuels* are considered sustainable and renewable alternatives that address the growing energy demand, reducing reliance on fossil fuels and contributing to lower energy costs. Noteworthy are the emerging technologies of *nanotechnology* and *genetic engineering*, which promote a more sustainable energy model and low-GHG-emission

The *Sustainability Policy* research front (red) ranks third, with 24% of the terms (6,225). The most influential descriptor is *sustainability*, with a score of 10,693; this reflects its relevance as a crucial approach to address climate change and promote sustainable development. This front outlines key challenges, such as inter-institutional coordination, the implementation of local policies, financing limitations, and community participation. It also emphasizes the importance of transparent governance, solid legal frameworks, and accountability to achieve more sustainable energy systems, promote climate justice, and ensure effective collaboration toward tangible results.

The fourth research front is *RE Storage* (yellow), accounting for 16% of the terms (4,055). Its most influential term is *lithium-ion battery* (Score = 6,017), highlighting the central role of energy transformation through new materials that enhance battery efficiency, durability, and cost-effectiveness. This front addresses technologies such as *hydrogen fuel cells* and *sodium oxide cells*, as well as *supercapacitors* for fast charging and longer lifespan in mobile devices [56]. The research aims to revolutionize energy storage and accelerate the transition to sustainable solutions.

The last research front, *Solar Energy Generation* (purple), represents 16% of the network terms (4,016). The most influential descriptor is *solar energy* (Score = 5,528). This interdisciplinary front focuses on optimizing photovoltaic and thermal systems through simulation, computer modeling, and advanced material development. Its main technologies include *silicon solar cells* and advanced electronic devices that aim to improve solar energy efficiency and generation, thus fostering innovation and a sustainable energy future.

3.2. Trends and Temporal Evolution of Global Scientific Production of RE

The 23 years analyzed were segmented into three temporal periods using the second derivative method, with overlay maps providing insights into the evolution of *renewable energy* (RE) research and its responses to global needs and technological advances.

The first period (2000-2012), termed Global Promotion of Renewable Energies, reflects early global efforts to promote RE research. The second period (2013-2019), referred to as the Global Expansion of Knowledge on RE, marks a stage of significant research consolidation and dissemination. The third period (2020-2022) captures dynamics driven by emerging technologies, focusing on strategic RE solution development.

Each period includes 30 descriptors ranked by influence (Score), linked to their research fronts (Fig. 5). The analysis is supplemented by Figure 6, which reports the dynamics and influence of RE research fronts, highlighting percentage trends and changes across the periods, and Figure 7, which focuses on the evolution of key RE terms by influence index (Score).

3.2.1. Global Promotion of RE (2000-2012)

This period includes 146,839 documents and 4,715 descriptors (Fig. 5), characterized by a broad diversity in RE approaches and advances, highlighting several research fronts reflecting global scientific and technological priorities at the time

Fig. 5. Evolution of Renewable Energy Research in the World.

Note: The following link allows the reader to view the maps and networks in VOSviewer: Cognitive map of temporal segment 1 available at the link (<https://tinyurl.com/2cq8ovrc>), segment 2 (<https://tinyurl.com/2cz8cmqa>), and segment 3 (<https://tinyurl.com/285heq24>).

Biofuel Generation (blue) is the most prominent research front, representing 33% of the scientific production, with 1,309 terms (Figure 6). This aligns with previous studies by Rizzi et al. [8], Aleixandre-Tudo et al. [9], and especially Manzano-Agugliaro et al. [5], who identified *biomass* as a key topic during this period. The most influential descriptor is *hydrogen* (Score = 5,107). The growing interest in researching *biohydrogen* production from organic waste is a promising alternative to reduce fossil fuel dependency, enhance energy security, and mitigate climate change. However, its adoption has faced significant challenges due to high production costs, necessitating technological innovations in *biotechnology* and

nanotechnology [57]. Research on *bioethanol* and *biodiesel* from *biomass* and *microalgae* has gained relevance as sustainable options. *Microalgae* have become an emerging research area due to their high lipid content and rapid growth, even on land unsuitable for agriculture [58]

Fig. 6. Evolution of Renewable Energy Research Fronts around the world.

The second most relevant front is *Renewable Energy Storage* (yellow), representing 27% of the production, with 1,068 descriptors, and integrating research topics from various fronts. *Fuel cells* (Score = 5,056) are the most relevant topic, showcasing interest in cutting-edge solutions for RE conversion and storage. Other emerging technologies include *hydrogen cells* [59], *sodium oxide cells* [5], and *microbial cells* [60]. Advanced materials, such as *carbon nanotubes* and *titanium dioxide*, are enhancing fuel cells' and batteries' efficiencies [54]. Likewise, storage systems like *lithium batteries* are widely used in mobile devices and electric vehicles [61, 62]; and *supercapacitors*, recognized for their high-density power and longer lifespan [63], are significantly transforming the energy storage outlook. Although the Scientific Systems (SS) related to this research front face challenges in design, cost, and energy efficiency, emerging research has opened new possibilities. For example, *microgrids* are an innovative solution that integrates wind, photovoltaic, and battery systems, promoting a sustainable and reliable approach for both the environment and consumers [55].

The third most relevant research front is *Structure in RE* (green), representing 17% of the total production with 726 descriptors. *Renewable energy* (Score=3,354) is the most mentioned term, highlighting a strong inclination toward areas related to wind and PV energy integration, like *hybrid systems* [9]; and the incorporation of technological systems in *electric vehicles*, demanding efficiency improvements and optimization for maximized performance and profitability. Moreover, a growing interest in integrating

advanced technologies to enhance hybrid energy SS performance has focused research in this period. Notably, *artificial intelligence* (AI) emerges as a key tool, facilitating decision-making in areas such as design, generation, distribution, and investment in RE [53].

The fourth research front focused on Solar Energy Generation (purple), representing 13% of the production with 844 descriptors. Although not top-ranked among analyzed references [5, 8, 9], its relevance lies in the integration of *solar* and *geothermal energy*, an expanding *hybrid system*. Another remarkable descriptor is *modeling* (Score = 2,973), reflecting the prominence of advanced modeling techniques in research. This approach has promoted important research areas, such as *cogeneration*, enabling simultaneous and efficient electricity and heat production [64]; *energy storage* [65]; and environmental impact mitigation strategies [66]. Among relevant technical advances are *computer-assisted fluid dynamics models*, used to evaluate the performance of hybrid systems like *solar chimneys* integrated with *geothermal energy*. These systems offer continuous energy production, minimize losses, and reduce consumer costs [67]. Additionally, hybrid system efficiency has been key, with emphasis on *heat transfer* and *energy storage*. Innovations such as *heat pumps*, *heat exchangers*, and *phase-change in nanomaterials* are key solutions for optimizing performance and promoting sustainability in this sector [68].

Sustainability Policy (red) is the last front, with 10% participation and 768 descriptors. The incidence of the terms *energy* and *sustainability* (Score = 2,556 and 1,869, respectively) reflects the priority of developing sustainable policies. Hence, research incorporating *energy sustainability* in key economic sectors, such as manufacturing and agroindustry, plays a crucial role in reducing GHG emissions and establishing climate resilience through efficient natural resource use [69].

During this period, research proposes policies that stimulate competitive technological innovation systems and promote emerging technology development, such as *solar energy*, through active innovation ecosystem actor participation [70]. Likewise, there is a growing trend toward strengthening human capital through *sustainable education*, focused on generating the necessary skills to implement these technologies and drive social innovation to ensure sustainable project viability [71].

3.2.2 Global Expansion of Knowledge on RE (2013-2019)

This period includes 334,182 documents and 12,994 descriptors, a 176% increase, reflecting the consolidation of RE research worldwide and a significant shift in research front rankings. *Structure in the RE* research front (green) now leads with 27% participation and 2,985 terms, a 411% descriptor increase from the previous period, validating its relevance (Figure 6). This aligns with Alexandre-Tudo et al.'s [9] findings, highlighting *wind energy* as the most influential study topic for this period.

With the highest score (14,847), *renewable energy* is the most prominent term in this segment, moving from fourth to first place due to a significant increase in research on *wind* and *solar photovoltaic energy* (Fig. 7). This progress is also linked to the growth of research on technologies applied to *electric vehicle* production, *energy storage systems*, and *RE grid integration*.

Fig. 7. Author Keywords on Renewable Energies by period.

Conversely, topics related to RE optimization have gained relevance through the implementation of techniques that improve energy system efficiency and demand management. Good examples include *genetic algorithms* and *particle swarm optimization*, used to solve complex electrical grid management problems. Research on this front has also been strengthened by the integration of advanced technologies such as *artificial intelligence* and *machine learning*. These technologies have enabled the optimization of hybrid RE systems, enhancing their performance, efficiency, and ability to address global energy challenges [40].

The second most relevant front is *Biofuel Generation* (blue) with 23% total participation and 2,908 descriptors, a 122% increase from the previous segment. *Biomass* consolidates as a key descriptor, ranking third with a Score of 12,019. According to Alexandre-Tudo et al. [9], *biomass*-related studies are among the most influential topics during the analyzed period. This front focuses on the production of *biofuels* such as *bioethanol*, *biodiesel*, *biogas*, and derivatives like *biochar* and *lignin*, a significant organic polymer. Likewise, there is growing interest in producing *hydrogen* through advanced organic processes, including *pyrolysis* [72, 73] and *enzymatic hydrolysis* [74]. This reflects the diversity in this front's research areas

Sustainability Policy (red) is in third position with 20% of the total terms, but a remarkable increase of 289% in the number of descriptors (2,990), making it one of the most influential fronts in scientific production. In comparison with the previous segment, the front climbed two positions, reflecting a growing interest by the global scientific community. *Sustainability* is the term with the highest Score (13,009), ranking in second for temporal period. This front addresses key terms related to *sustainability*, *environment*, and *environmental impacts*, which can be grouped in one single concept.

The fundamental concept of Sustainability has become relevant in developing policies that promote environmental protection, climate change mitigation, and GHG emission reduction. Research on *circular economy policies* are essential for advancing on sustainability, particularly in terms of reducing *carbon footprints* and *efficient waste management*. It is worth mentioning the influence of countries like China and India, who despite their high fossil fuel consumption, have become global leaders in integrating sustainable energies and implementing policies aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [75, 76].

The *Solar Energy Generation* front (purple) has remained in fourth position, with 17% of participation. Although, it has experienced a significant 130% growth in the number of terms compared to the previous segment. The most relevant descriptor is *solar energy* with a network influence of 7,495. This front highlights research on the hybrid integration of solar and geothermal energy, a line of research that has been consolidated within the global RE Scientific Systems.

One of the most important topics in this research front is the technology related to concentrated solar energy, which uses mirrors and lenses to focus sunlight and generate high-temperature steam [77, 78]. When combined with the *organic Rankine cycle*, it converts low-temperature heat into electricity, becoming an efficient cogeneration system [79]. This system allows simultaneous production of electricity and heat, useful for domestic consumption, whether for heating or common appliances use [80]. Likewise, research on hybrid energies has focused on improving heat transfer, thermal storage [81], and the use of innovative materials like *nanofluids*, which are employed in solar panels to enhance their thermal performance [82, 83].

The last in the rank, losing three positions from the previous period, is *RE Storage* (yellow), representing 13% of the terms. Its most relevant term is *lithium-ion battery*, with a Score of 6,732, reflecting an improvement compared to other energy storage related terms. Additionally, there is still a strong influence from the lines of research that focused on *sodium batteries* and *supercapacitors*, which require improvements in durability and performance as storage devices [84].

A remarkable experimental initiative that emerged during this period is the use of new materials, such as *graphene* and *nanocomposites*, which aim to improve the efficiency and energy storage capacity [85, 86]. These advanced materials are characterized by their high electrical conductivity, thermal conductivity, and a lower environmental impact compared to other nanotechnologies [87]. Furthermore, there is progress on research related to energy harvesting and conversion, through the study of chemical reactions in batteries, such as *electrocatalysis*, as well as the design of *electrodes* to optimize energy conversion during its input and output [88].

3.2.3 Global Transformation of Renewable Energy (2020-2022)

The third segment includes the analysis of 281,668 documents published over a three-year period, which represents an important increase of scientific production in renewable energies, sustainability, and environment; this front is also enhanced with 406 additional descriptors that open new lines of research, such as *Artificial Intelligence and Renewable Energies* (light blue), reflecting the integration of emerging technologies in this field (Fig. 5).

Global Transformation of RE consists of six research fronts. *Structure in RE* is in first place with 23% participation, and 2,272 terms. The term with the highest Score is *renewable energy* (15,847), which, even though is still relevant, has dropped to second place in this temporal segment. The number of descriptors found in this segment has decreased significantly by 24%, reflecting the dynamic nature of the research systems through time.

The rearrangement and the surge of new descriptors reflect the transition to new lines of research, with a significant growth observed in topics such as *wind-photovoltaic hybrid systems*, integrated with electrical grids. Scientific advances in this area are partly due to the growth of the electric vehicle market, driven by *AI innovations* and the leadership of companies like Tesla, BYD, Xiaopeng, and NIO. In particular, Chinese companies stand out for their competitiveness, supported by the existence of 605,000 companies that are part of the supply chain of RE and electric vehicles in 2023 [89].

Sustainability Policy (red) ranks second with a 20% participation and 3,718 terms, reflecting a 24% growth. In terms of representation, this front has experienced the best evolution over the 23 years of analysis, due to the integration of 718 new research terms of high impact. The most relevant keyword is *Sustainability* with a Score of 18,128.

The topics listed in the top rank reflect a process of integration of the international policies for sustainable development. The design of a global policy includes social, economic, and environmental dimensions [90]. Among the interdisciplinary policies, *innovation processes for energy transition* stands out; this policy and particularly the SDG-7 must be adopted by the UN country members as part of the 2030 agenda. Other topics that have been addressed are *energy optimization* and *business competitiveness using sustainable processes*, such as *circular economy*, *corporate social responsibility*, and *product life cycle* [91].

In third place is *Solar Energy Generation* (purple), representing 20% of the total, with 1,929 descriptors. This front experiences a slight decrease of 0.8% in comparison with the previous segment. The term with the highest Score is *Solar Energy*, with a value of 6,731, even though it is a smaller score than in the previous segment when it was 7,495. Nevertheless, this research front continues moving forward and consolidating the development of *solar-geothermal hybrid systems*.

Among the most relevant emerging technologies are *energy conversion systems*, which use innovative mechanisms to improve both efficiency and sustainable energy production. Remarkable examples of these include *fluid dynamics*, which enable the connection of multiple systems to convert the potential energy of fluid movement into electricity [92], and the *closed-cycle engine system* which generates electricity through a piston movement and temperature differences leverage to drive the conversion process [93].

Biofuel Generation (blue) is in fourth place, with a 17% participation and 2,504 descriptors. This front dropped two positions from the last segment. Despite its decline, the term *Biomass* (Score = 8,285) remains as the most representative of the front, although it has lost influence because other topics have repositioned.

Thus, lines of research on *bioethanol*, *biodiesel*, *biogas*, *microalgae*, and derivatives such as *biochar* and *lignin* still continue to consolidate in this field. Moreover, significant innovations in production processes, such as *enzymatic hydrolysis for hydrogen production* and the use of *catalysts for biomass conversion*, have emerged opening new possibilities for improving production efficiency.

This front has shown a steady accumulation of knowledge over the last 23 years, resulting in a solid and recognized scientific system that has become a fundamental pillar in the energy transition and the efforts to mitigate global warming.

Artificial Intelligence and RE is in fifth place, with 1,929 descriptors and a 13% participation. In this front, the term *machine learning* stands out as the most influential, with a Score of 10,009. Although the descriptors associated with this field were found in the previous segment, their recent convergence reflects a significant shift in the scientific and technological paradigm. This front has also become an accelerator factor for global research production, driving the optimization of systems and processes in

renewable energy, thanks to its integration with other research fronts, particularly with *Renewable Energy Structure* and *Biofuel Generation*.

Within the thematic lines of this new front (light-blue in the map) are the development of *algorithms and mathematical models* for predicting and classifying data from systems related to the generation, transformation, transport, demand, and loss of energy [94]. A clear example of its application is the use of prediction and forecasting, which are essential tools in anticipating energy demand and diagnosing failures in production systems [95]. These advances are significantly improving energy performance, reducing operational costs, and enhancing energy grid stability [96]. This has been made possible by integrating advanced sensors and new materials, key components in RE systems that enable real-time data collection and the generation of accurate diagnostics for more efficient decision-making.

In last place is the *RE Storage* front (yellow), with a 7% participation and 1,803 terms. The descriptor with the highest Score is *lithium-ion battery*, reaching a value of 5,419. On one hand, this research front continues to address key topics regarding *energy storage*, such as improving and preserving *lithium-ion* and *sodium batteries*, as well as *supercapacitors*. Focusing on lines of research involving *nanocomposites* like *graphene* and *carbon particle nanotechnology*, aiming to enhance the electrical capacity and stability of lithium-ion batteries [97]. And, on the other hand, there is progress shown in research related to energy storage in *fuel cells*, particularly in optimizing *electrochemical reactions* for *hydrogen evolution*. This process aims to improve the efficiency of the reaction that splits the water molecule, producing hydrogen and gaseous oxygen [98], which could enhance the viability of new, more sustainable energy sources.

4. Conclusions

This study has revealed the scientific structure and main research fronts in Renewable Energies through an exhaustive analysis of scientific literature from 2000 to 2022, presenting 25,728 frequently used researcher terms. This study offers a renewed perspective on RE development as a discipline. Through author keyword analysis, we identified the most relevant current themes. Topics such as *sustainability*, *circular economy*, and new technologies like AI and *energy storage* are key elements in designing R&D strategies to address future energy challenges.

Using the second derivative, we segmented the study period into three temporal phases and, with overlay maps, clearly studied the evolution of RE research fronts. This analysis indicates the consolidation of three key fronts: Structure of Renewable Energies (wind-photovoltaic hybrid research), Biofuel Generation (*biomass*), and Sustainability Policies (SDGs), which have shown sustained growth. Alongside, two complementary fronts emerge: RE Storage (*batteries*) and Solar Energy Generation (*solar-geothermal hybrid*). We also identified a new emerging front: *Artificial Intelligence* and RE, characterized by its integration and acceleration of global energy transition.

This integrated approach, combining bibliometric techniques with in-depth emerging trend analysis, not only contributes to understanding RE evolution but also provides a strategic framework for designing scientific and technological policies that guide the transition to a more sustainable and efficient energy system. The methodology used can be extrapolated to any scientific field to reveal its underlying structure and main research fronts.

Limitations and Future Research

This research primarily used the Scopus database, considering approximately 800,000 documents. Future research could incorporate other bibliographic and patent information sources to complement these results.

A second proposal is to analyze RE production by country and compare it against global production to establish research competencies and convergences. This analysis would help identify potential unique research contributors and propose potential international research collaborations.

The third proposal involves using a heuristic method with open-access artificial intelligence to classify the 25,728 author keywords related to the six renewable energies, generating a classification matrix and assigning descriptors to each RE. Expert supervision through random checks will ensure classification quality. These databases will allow refining searches and overlaying relationships between countries concerning each RE type.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest regarding the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Funding information

This work is supported by the Consejo Nacional de Humanidades, Ciencias y Tecnologías (Conahcyt) of Mexico, which provided funding through the scholarship (803848; 2021-000018-02NACF-24404) and the RESPONSIBLE project (PID2021-128429NB-I00) funded by MCIN / AEI / 10.13039/501100011033 / ERDF, EU.

Supplementary Information

The Supplementary Information includes three key sections: Part A: The thesaurus developed for the analysis, which standardizes the author keywords; Part B: The coding used for time segmentation; and Part C: The datasets employed to conduct the analysis.

Data Availability

Related datasets can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115640>

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